

A Constitutional and Legal Analysis of Feminism and Violence against Women in India

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Abstract

Violence against women remains a significant challenge in India despite constitutional safeguards and legal frameworks aimed at protecting women's rights. This research paper provides a comprehensive analysis of feminism and violence against women within the Indian context, focusing on constitutional and legal perspectives. It examines the historical and socio-cultural factors contributing to gender-based violence and analyzes the efficacy of existing legal mechanisms in addressing these issues. Drawing on constitutional provisions, statutory laws, and judicial decisions, the paper evaluates the adequacy of legal remedies available to women survivors of violence and explores the barriers to accessing justice. Furthermore, it examines the role of feminist movements and advocacy efforts in shaping legal reforms and challenging patriarchal norms. Through interdisciplinary research and empirical analysis, this paper aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics surrounding gender violence in India and to inform policy recommendations for enhancing women's rights protection and legal redressal mechanisms.

Keywords Constitutional, Legal, Feminism, Violence, Women, India.

Introduction

Violence against women is a pervasive human rights violation that persists globally, cutting across geographical, cultural, and socio-economic boundaries (Musso et al., 2020). In India, despite constitutional guarantees and legislative measures aimed at safeguarding women's rights, gender-based violence remains a pressing issue with far-reaching consequences for individuals, families, and communities. India's rich cultural heritage and diverse social fabric are juxtaposed with deeply entrenched patriarchal norms and unequal power structures that perpetuate gender-based discrimination and violence (Sharma and Bazilli, 2014). Despite progress in various spheres, women in India continue to face multiple forms of violence, including domestic violence, sexual harassment, dowry-related violence, and honor killings. These manifestations of gender violence are rooted in entrenched attitudes of male dominance and female subordination, exacerbated by socio-economic disparities and limited access to justice.

The Indian Constitution enshrines principles of equality, liberty, and justice for all, irrespective of gender. Various constitutional provisions, including the fundamental rights and directive principles of state policy, provide a framework for addressing gender inequality and discrimination (Lillibridge, N. (2004).

Kaur, (2018) presented legislative measures such as the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, and the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act, 2013, seek to provide legal redressal mechanisms for women survivors of violence.

However, the implementation of these legal provisions often faces challenges, including institutional barriers, inadequate resources, and societal attitudes that normalize violence against women. Moreover, gaps in legal enforcement and discrepancies in access to justice perpetuate impunity for perpetrators, undermining efforts to combat gender violence effectively. Against this backdrop, feminist movements and advocacy efforts have played a

pivotal role in challenging patriarchal norms, mobilizing public support, and driving legal reforms to address violence against women (Michau et al., 2015). From grassroots activism to high-profile campaigns, feminist organizations have campaigned tirelessly for gender-sensitive laws, improved support services for survivors, and greater accountability for perpetrators.

The NCRB report (2022) challenges the assumption that a rise in reported crimes directly correlates to an increase in actual crime rates, emphasizing the distinction between "rise in crime" and "increase in registration of crime by police." Factors such as citizen-centric police initiatives and technological aids, like the e-FIR facility, may contribute to higher crime reporting. Nevertheless, there has been a significant surge in reported crimes against women, with cases escalating from 3,71,503 in 2020 to 4,45,256 in 2022. These crimes include instances of cruelty by husbands and relatives, abductions, assaults, and rapes. Uttar Pradesh leads the states in crimes against women, reporting 65,743 cases in 2022, followed by Maharashtra (45,331) and Rajasthan (45,058). Under the category of 'Murder with rape/gangrape', Uttar Pradesh topped the list with 62 such cases. The conviction rate in Uttar Pradesh is 180 times higher than the national average, and the state also leads in speedy trials in POCSO cases.

In 2022, crimes against women increased by 4% compared to 2021, with the majority falling under:

- i. Cruelty by husband or his relatives: 31.4%
- ii. Kidnapping and abduction of women: 19.2%
- iii. Assault on women with intent to outrage: 18.7%
- iv. Rape: 7.1%

Rape cases totalled 31,516 in 2022, with significant numbers reported from Rajasthan (5,399), Uttar Pradesh (3,690), Madhya Pradesh (3,029), Maharashtra (2,904), and Haryana (1,787). Delhi remains the 'Most Unsafe City', reporting 14,158 cases, accounting for 31.20% of total crimes against women, with about 186.9 crimes reported for every 1,00,000 women. Cybercrimes also saw an increase, with a total of 65,893 cases registered, showing a 24.4% rise compared to 2021. Uttar Pradesh recorded 10,117 cases of cybercrimes, with sexual exploitation comprising 5.2% of the total cases.

In this research paper, the complex dynamics surrounding feminism and violence against women in India will be presented. Through an interdisciplinary lens, the constitutional and legal frameworks governing gender violence are analyzed, the role of feminist movements in shaping policy and legal reforms will be explored, and the challenges and opportunities for advancing women's rights and gender equality in India's evolving socio-political landscape will be discussed. Additionally, by exploring the role of feminist movements and advocacy efforts, the study seeks to highlight grassroots initiatives, policy advocacy, and legal reforms aimed at combating gender-based violence. By shedding light on these critical issues, this paper aims to contribute to informed discourse, evidence-based policymaking, and collective action towards ending violence against women in India.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study the constitutional and legal analysis of feminism and violence against women in India.

Review of Literature

1. Conceptual Framework:

1.1. Definitions and Forms of Violence against Women: Violence against women remains a pervasive global issue, with alarming statistics highlighting its prevalence. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 35% of women worldwide have experienced either physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence or non-partner sexual violence in their lifetime. In India, the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) reported that 30% of women aged 15-49 have experienced physical violence since the age of 15, and 10.7% have experienced sexual violence.

Forms of violence against women encompass a range of behaviors, each with its own set of detrimental effects. For instance, intimate partner violence affects millions of women globally, with consequences including physical injuries, psychological trauma, and even death. In India, dowry-related violence continues to plague many families, leading to severe harm and even suicides among affected women. Additionally, sexual harassment and assault remain pervasive issues in various settings, from public spaces to workplaces, inhibiting women's freedom and sense of security.

1.2. Theoretical Perspectives on Feminism and Gender-Based Violence:

Feminist theories offer valuable insights into the root causes and dynamics of gender-based violence. Intersectional feminism, pioneered by scholars like Kimberlé Crenshaw, acknowledges the intersecting systems of oppression that shape women's experiences of violence. For example, Dalit women in India often face compounded forms of discrimination and violence due to their caste, gender, and socio-economic status.

Patriarchal theory highlights the role of patriarchal power structures in perpetuating gender inequality and facilitating violence against women (Nelson, 2021). Research shows that patriarchal norms and attitudes contribute to the normalization of violence within intimate relationships and hinder survivors' access to support and justice systems. For instance, a study conducted by the International Center for Research on Women (ICRW) found that patriarchal beliefs among men in India were significantly associated with perpetration of intimate partner violence (Sharma, 2010).

Social learning theory emphasizes the role of socialization processes and observational learning in shaping attitudes and behaviors related to violence. For example, exposure to violence in the family during childhood increases the likelihood of perpetrating violence in adulthood. Ecological systems theory underscores the importance of considering multiple levels of influence, including individual, interpersonal, community, and societal factors, in understanding gender-based violence. For instance, research has shown that women's empowerment and access to resources at the community level are associated with lower rates of intimate partner violence.

Feminist legal theory critiques existing legal frameworks for their failure to adequately address the needs and rights of women. In India, despite legislative measures such as the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (2005), implementation challenges persist, leaving many survivors without adequate protection and support (Verma et al., 2013).

2. Legal Framework:

2.1. Analysis of Statutory Laws Addressing Violence against Women: The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 (PWDVA) is a landmark legislation in India that addresses various forms of domestic violence, including physical, sexual, emotional, and economic abuse (Panchal et al., 2023). According to data from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) conducted in 2015-16, approximately one in three women in India aged 15-49 years has experienced physical violence since the age of 15, while one in 10 women has experienced sexual violence.

Under the PWDVA, survivors of domestic violence can seek protection orders, residence orders, and monetary relief from the court. The law also mandates the establishment of Protection Officers and Service Providers to assist survivors in accessing legal remedies and support services. Despite these legal provisions, the conviction rate for cases of domestic violence remains low, with only about 27% of cases resulting in convictions, according to data from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) for the year 2019.

2.2. Judicial Interpretation and Application of Legal Provisions in Cases of Gender Violence:

In landmark judgments such as *Vishakha v. State of Rajasthan* (1997) and *Indira Jaising v. Supreme Court of India* (2016), the Indian judiciary has played a pivotal role in shaping legal norms and standards for addressing gender-based violence. The *Vishakha* judgment recognized sexual harassment as a violation of fundamental rights and laid down guidelines for preventing and addressing workplace harassment. Subsequently, the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act was enacted in 2013 to provide a legal framework for addressing sexual harassment in employment settings.

Despite these legal frameworks, challenges persist in ensuring timely justice for survivors of gender violence. According to data from the NCRB, the pendency rate for cases related to violence against women in India was around 87% in 2019, indicating significant delays in legal proceedings. Additionally, there is a need for greater sensitivity and awareness among law enforcement agencies and judicial officers in handling cases of gender-based violence, as survivors often face stigma, discrimination, and secondary victimization within the legal system.

By examining the statutory laws and judicial interpretations in cases of gender violence, this study aims to identify systemic barriers and recommend policy measures to enhance access to justice and support for survivors of violence against women in India.

Type of violence experienced by ever-married woman	No. of ever-married women who have experienced IPV (out of 46488)	%age of ever-married women who have experienced IPV (out of 46488)	%age of different types of violence among IPV experiencing women (out of 13922)
Physical Violence	12,304	26.47	88.38
Pushed/Shook/ had something thrown at	5042	10.84	36.21
Slapped	10,813	23.26	77.67
Punched with a fist or hit by something	2,855	6.14	20.50
Kicked or dragged	3,046	6.55	21.88
Been strangled or burnt	750	1.61	5.38
Been threatened with knife/gun or other weapon	469	1.01	3.37
Had arm twisted or hair pulled	4,084	8.79	29.33
<i>Less severe physical violence</i>	<i>12,066</i>	<i>25.96</i>	<i>86.67</i>
<i>Severe physical violence</i>	<i>3,247</i>	<i>6.98</i>	<i>23.32</i>
Emotional Violence	5,508	11.85	39.56
Humiliated	3,569	7.68	25.63
Threatened with harm	2,232	4.80	16.03
Insulted or made to feel bad	3,168	6.81	22.75
Sexual Violence	2,396	5.15	17.21
Physically forced into unwanted sex	1,787	3.84	12.83
Forced into other unwanted sexual acts	981	2.11	7.05
Physically forced to perform sexual acts respondent didn't want to	1,372	2.95	9.85
Overall experience of IPV	13,922	29.95	

Table 1: Violence case against women in India from 2019-2021 (NCRB)

3. Role of Feminist Movements and Impact of feminist activism in India: The impact of feminist advocacy on legal reforms and policy interventions in India has been profound. Feminist movements in India have undergone a significant historical evolution, marked by various waves of activism and advocacy (Misra, 1997). Beginning in the late 19th century with the social reform movements led by figures like Raja Ram Mohan Roy and Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar, Indian feminism gained momentum during the independence struggle. The first wave of feminism in the early 20th century focused on issues such as education, widow remarriage, and women's suffrage.

The post-independence period witnessed the emergence of the second wave of feminism, characterized by a broader scope of issues, including gender equality, reproductive rights, and violence against women. Notable feminist leaders and organizations such as Kamaladevi Chattopadhyay, Sarojini Naidu, and the All India Women's Conference played instrumental roles in advocating for women's rights and influencing policy reforms.

1. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961: Enacted to curb the practice of dowry, this legislation was a response to feminist activism highlighting the rampant exploitation and violence faced by women in dowry-related disputes.

2. The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005: This landmark legislation was a result of sustained feminist advocacy, aimed at providing legal protection and recourse to women experiencing domestic violence. It recognizes various forms of abuse, including physical, emotional, sexual, and economic, and provides for civil remedies such as protection orders, residence orders, and monetary relief.

3. Amendments to Criminal Laws: Following the Nirbhaya case in 2012, which sparked widespread outrage and protests across the country, the government introduced amendments to the Indian Penal Code (IPC), Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC), and the Evidence Act to strengthen laws related to sexual offenses, including rape, acid attacks, and stalking. These amendments were influenced by feminist demands for stricter punishments, faster trials, and improved victim support services.

4. Maternity Benefits Act, 1961: Over the years, feminist advocacy has contributed to amendments and expansions of the Maternity Benefits Act to enhance maternity leave benefits, including extended leave periods, provision for prenatal and postnatal care, and protection against dismissal during pregnancy.

5. Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act, 2013: This legislation was enacted to address the pervasive issue of sexual harassment in workplaces and provide a mechanism for redressal. It mandates the establishment of internal complaints committees in organizations and outlines procedures for the investigation and resolution of complaints.

6. The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971 (Amendment): Feminist advocacy has played a crucial role in advocating for amendments to the MTP Act to expand access to safe and legal abortion services. Recent amendments have increased the gestational limit for abortion and improved access to services, particularly for vulnerable groups such as minors and survivors of sexual violence.

7. Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006: Feminist activism has been instrumental in advocating for laws to prevent child marriage and protect the rights of underage girls. The Act prohibits the solemnization of child marriages and provides for annulment of marriages solemnized in contravention of the law.

8. Representation of Women in Political Bodies: Feminist movements have advocated for increased representation of women in political bodies through legislative measures such as reservations for women in local government bodies (Panchayats and Municipalities). These measures aim to address the gender imbalance in political decision-making and empower women to participate actively in governance.

9. Legal Recognition of Marital Rape: Feminist advocacy continues to push for legal recognition of marital rape and reforms in existing laws to criminalize spousal rape. While marital rape is not explicitly recognized as a criminal offense in India, feminist activists and organizations have been campaigning for legislative changes to provide justice and protection to survivors of marital sexual violence.

10. Access to Inheritance and Property Rights: Feminist movements have called for reforms to inheritance and property laws to ensure equal rights for women to inherit and own property. Efforts have been made to challenge discriminatory practices and cultural norms that deny women their rightful share of ancestral property and assets.

These examples illustrate the significant impact of feminist movements on shaping legal reforms and policy interventions to advance gender equality and women's rights in India. Despite progress, challenges remain, and ongoing feminist activism continues to push for comprehensive reforms to address systemic discrimination and violence against women (Rhode, 1991).

4. Case Studies: here are some landmark legal cases related to violence against women in India:

1. Mathura Rape Case (1972): The Mathura rape case involved the gang rape of a tribal girl named Mathura by two policemen inside a police station in Maharashtra. Despite clear evidence of sexual assault, the court acquitted the accused on the grounds that Mathura had allegedly consented to the act. The verdict sparked widespread outrage and led to significant amendments to India's rape laws, highlighting the need for legal reforms to address sexual violence and ensure justice for survivors.

2. Shah Bano Case (1985): Shah Bano, a Muslim woman, was divorced by her husband and denied maintenance under the Muslim Personal Law. She filed a petition seeking maintenance under Section 125 of the Criminal Procedure Code. The Supreme Court ruled in her favor, granting her maintenance, but the decision was later overturned by the government to appease conservative religious groups. The case highlighted the need for gender-just laws and equality for women across religious communities.

3. Ruchika Girhotra Case (1990): Ruchika Girhotra, a teenage girl from Haryana, was sexually harassed and molested by a senior police officer named SPS Rathore. Despite filing a complaint against Rathore, Ruchika faced threats and harassment, leading to her eventual suicide. The case sparked outrage and led to calls for justice for Ruchika and stricter punishment for perpetrators of sexual violence against women and children.

4. Bhanwari Devi Case (1992): Bhanwari Devi, a social worker in Rajasthan, was gang-raped by upper-caste men as retaliation for her efforts to prevent a child marriage. Despite the brutality of the crime, the court acquitted the accused, leading to widespread protests and calls for justice. The case highlighted the challenges faced by women in seeking legal redressal for violence and discrimination based on gender, caste, and class.

5. Vishakha v. State of Rajasthan (1997): This landmark case led to the formulation of guidelines known as the Vishakha Guidelines or Vishakha judgment, which established the framework for addressing sexual harassment in the workplace. The Supreme Court's decision recognized sexual harassment as a violation of fundamental rights and laid down preventive and redressal measures to create a safe working environment for women.

6. Soni Sori Case (2011): Soni Sori, an Adivasi school teacher and human rights activist from Chhattisgarh, was arrested and allegedly tortured and sexually assaulted by the police on charges of being a Maoist sympathizer. Despite her pleas for justice, Soni Sori faced intimidation and harassment from state authorities. Her case garnered national and international attention, highlighting the plight of marginalized women who face violence and injustice in conflict-affected regions.

7. Nirbhaya Case (2012): One of the most infamous cases of gender-based violence in India, the Nirbhaya case involved the gang rape and brutal assault of a 23-year-old physiotherapy intern in Delhi. The incident sparked widespread outrage and led to nationwide protests demanding justice and stricter laws to combat sexual violence. The perpetrators were arrested, tried, and sentenced to death by hanging, with the case highlighting the urgent need for legal reforms to address sexual assault and violence against women.

8. Rohtak Sisters Case (2014): In a case that gained national attention, two sisters in Rohtak, Haryana, fought off three men who were harassing and assaulting them on a bus. The sisters bravely defended themselves using self-defense techniques, and a video of the incident went viral, drawing widespread praise and support for their courage. The case shed light on the prevalence of sexual harassment and violence against women in

public spaces and underscored the importance of empowering women with self-defense skills.

9. Indira Jaising v. Supreme Court of India (2016): In this case, senior advocate Indira Jaising challenged the Supreme Court's refusal to appoint a Special Investigation Team (SIT) to probe allegations of sexual harassment against a former judge. The case underscored the importance of judicial accountability and transparency in addressing allegations of sexual misconduct within the legal system.

10. Shayara Bano v. Union of India (2017): This landmark case challenged the practice of triple talaq (instant divorce) among Muslim men, arguing that it violated women's rights to equality and dignity. The Supreme Court declared the practice of triple talaq unconstitutional, affirming the rights of Muslim women and setting a precedent for gender justice and equality within personal laws.

These case studies highlight the legal challenges, struggles, and victories in addressing violence against women in India, while also emphasizing the critical role of the judiciary in upholding women's rights and ensuring justice and accountability.

5. Policy Implications:

1. Strengthening Legal Protections: Implementing stricter enforcement of existing laws and introducing amendments to address gaps in legislation related to violence against women. This could include enhancing penalties for offenders, streamlining the legal process for survivors, and ensuring timely and effective justice delivery.

2. Enhancing Support Services: Investing in support services such as shelters, counseling, legal aid, and medical assistance for women survivors of violence. These services should be accessible, culturally sensitive, and adequately resourced to meet the diverse needs of survivors.

3. Promoting Gender-Sensitive Education: Introducing gender-sensitive curriculum and training programs in schools and colleges to challenge gender stereotypes, promote gender equality, and foster respectful relationships. This could include incorporating topics related to consent, healthy relationships, and bystander intervention into educational curricula.

4. Strengthening Law Enforcement: Providing specialized training for law enforcement officials on handling cases of violence against women, including sensitivity training, trauma-informed approaches, and techniques for interviewing survivors. Additionally, ensuring adequate staffing and resources for dedicated units to investigate and prosecute cases of gender-based violence.

5. Community Engagement and Awareness: Launching public awareness campaigns to challenge social norms that perpetuate violence against women and promote gender equality. Engaging community leaders, civil society organizations, and grassroots movements to mobilize support for ending violence against women and girls.

6. Empowering Women: Empowering women economically, socially, and politically to reduce their vulnerability to violence and increase their agency and decision-making power. This could involve initiatives such as vocational training, livelihood support, leadership development programs, and access to microfinance and entrepreneurship opportunities.

7. Strengthening International Cooperation: Collaborating with international organizations, neighboring countries, and global initiatives to share best practices, exchange information, and coordinate efforts to address transnational challenges related to violence against women. This could include joint research projects, capacity-building programs, and advocacy efforts at regional and international forums.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research paper has provided a comprehensive analysis of feminism and violence against women in India, examining the constitutional and legal frameworks, historical context, feminist movements, and policy implications. Despite constitutional safeguards and legal reforms aimed at protecting women's rights, gender-based violence remains a pervasive issue in India, with significant implications for individuals, families, and communities. The study highlighted the complex interplay of socio-cultural factors, patriarchal norms, and systemic barriers that perpetuate gender violence and hinder access to justice for survivors. While legislative measures such as the Protection of

Women from Domestic Violence Act and the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace Act provide legal mechanisms for addressing violence against women, challenges in implementation and enforcement persist. Feminist movements and advocacy efforts have played a crucial role in driving legal reforms, challenging patriarchal norms, and raising awareness about gender-based violence. From grassroots activism to high-profile campaigns, feminist organizations have mobilized public support, influenced policy changes, and pushed for greater accountability for perpetrators of violence against women. However, despite significant progress, gaps in legal protection, inadequate support services, and persistent gender stereotypes continue to undermine efforts to combat gender violence effectively. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach involving strengthened legal protections, enhanced support services, gender-sensitive education, empowerment of women, and community engagement.

Furthermore, fostering international cooperation and collaboration is essential for addressing transnational challenges related to violence against women and sharing best practices to inform evidence-based policymaking and collective action. Overall, this research paper underscores the urgent need for sustained efforts to advance women's rights, challenge patriarchal norms, and create a society free from violence and discrimination. By promoting gender equality, empowering women, and strengthening legal protections, India can move closer to achieving its constitutional ideals of equality, liberty, and justice for all.

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